

DELIVERABLE

Project Acronym: CARARE
Grant Agreement number: 250445
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D.6.6.2 Project web environment and dissemination materials

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Project co-funded by the European Commission within the ICT Policy Support Programme		
Dissemination Level		
P	Public	X
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

Revision History

Revision	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
Draft	12/5/10	K Fernie	MDR	First draft
Final	17/5/10	K Fernie	MDR	Final version following review by Henrik Jarl Hansen and Sheena Bassett

Statement of originality:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Table of Contents

1.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
2.	PROJECT LOGO	4
3.	PROJECT WEB ENVIRONMENT	4
4.	DISSEMINATION MATERIALS	9
5.	REFERENCES	12

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the project web environment and the initial set of dissemination materials that have been produced for use by project partners.

The project web environment (<http://www.carare.eu>) was launched at the project kick-off meeting and went live in month two of the project. The aim of the website is to provide information about the project to national heritage agencies, heritage organisations, research institutions, archaeology museums and interested professionals and students in Europe and also to provide an Intranet for members of the project consortium.

The public part of the website includes information about the project and the consortium, information about its activities, news, events, project resources and a section for the CARARE community. The website is linked to dissemination tools and registered users of the website will receive copies of the CARARE eNewsletter. The site is also linked to social networks via groups which have been established for the wider CARARE community on LinkedIn and Facebook.

For partners, the website provides access to an Intranet. Registered partners are provided with tools to enable them to upload and edit content within the intranet, and to make use of the partner discussion forum.

An initial set of dissemination materials has been established including the project logo, templates for print materials and for PowerPoint presentations, a CARARE Essentials presentation, project information briefing and press notices.

In the first instance the project web environment and dissemination materials have been made available in English. The project plans to offer materials in all partner languages and work is currently in progress to translate the initial set of materials.

2. Project logo

The project logo was based on the Europeana brand guidelines and on the communication tools provided by Europeana. The logo is formed from the 'e' of Europeana and integrates images of archaeological sites, artefacts and historic buildings which were provided for use by members of the consortium. The logo is intended to illustrate a juxtaposition of cultures, of 2D and 3D objects, and people with the flashes, shapes and colours used to represent the dynamics of new forms and new ideas in line with the Europeana brand.

The logo was designed by Carol Usher of MDR Partners and was approved by the project partners. It has been made available in various sizes and formats to partners on the project website for use in print and web publications.

3. Project web environment

A project website was made available (<http://www.carare.eu>) by the second month of the project and was demonstrated to partners at the project kick-off meeting. The aim of the website is to provide information about the project to national heritage agencies, heritage organisations, research institutions, archaeology museums and interested professionals and students in Europe and also to provide an Intranet for members of the project consortium.

The public part of the website includes:

- About - the project description and consortium
- Activities – the work packages and events
- News
- Resources
- Community
- Links

The project Intranet includes:

- Forum (partner discussion area)
- Project management
- Work packages (meeting reports etc)
- Reviews
- Deliverables
- Communication tools

The website was initially made available in English. The project plans to make the public pages of the site available in each of the partner languages and alternate language content is currently in development.

The project home page is illustrated below:

The screenshot shows the website's home page. At the top right, there are links for 'Site map', 'Register', 'Login', and a language dropdown set to 'English'. The main header features the 'europeana carare project' logo on the left and a decorative graphic of overlapping circles on the right. Below the header is a navigation menu with 'About', 'Activities', 'News', 'Resources', 'Community', and 'Links'. The main content area is titled 'Home' and contains a 'Home' section with a description of the CARARE project and a quote: "Bringing content for archaeology and historic buildings to Europeana users." Below this is a 'Partner of' section with the europeana logo and the tagline 'think culture'. To the right is a 'News' section with three items: 'European Parliament: Europeana', 'Euromed photography award launches', and 'Europeana Public Domain Charter published'.

The website has been provided in English in the first instance. The project plans to offer the public sections of the website in all of the partner languages and work is currently in progress to prepare translations of the initial content.

The website incorporates a registration facility to enable members of the CARARE community to register to receive newsletters and also to interact with the website (for example by adding comments about events, or rating news items).

An email distribution system has been set up to distribute the CARARE eNewsletter to stakeholders and registered users of the CARARE website are automatically added to the stakeholder database.

CARARE partners are able to register on the project website to gain access to the partner area. Access is provided to tools from the content management to enable partners to edit and upload content within the partner area of the site. The partner area of the website is illustrated below:

Site map My profile Logout (KateF PartnerTest) English

europeana carare project

About Activities News Resources Community Links Partner Area

Home > Partner Area > Work Packages

ez Article OpenOffice.org ?

Work Packages

WP	Title	Lead	Start month	End month
1	Project management	MDR	1	36
2	Preparing and enabling	KUAS	1	12
3	Testing and prototyping	DCU	6	30
4	Harvesting and aggregating	CHA	12	36
5	3D and Virtual Reality	VisDim	6	30
6	Dissemination	MDR	1	36
7	Sustainability	ADS	1	36

- Forum
- Project management
- Work Packages**
- Work package 2
- Work package 3
- Work package 4
- Work package 5
- Work package 6
- Work package 7
- Reviews
- Deliverables
- Communication tools

A discussion forum has been set up within the partner area to provide partners with a facility to discuss work in progress:

About Activities News Resources Community Links Partner Area

Home > Partner Area > Forum

Forum

New topic

Topic	Replies	Last reply
Joining the network Luc Chase	1	Luc Chase » 22/02/2010 1:03 pm
VAST Anetta Kepczynska-Walczak	0	
Communications working group Kate Fernie	0	

- Forum**
- Project management
- Work Packages
- Reviews
- Deliverables
- Communication tools

Share |

Plans include developing a CARARE community via links from the project website to social networking sites such as Facebook and LinkedIn. The community homepage is illustrated below:

The CARARE LinkedIn group currently has 68 members, the discussion page is illustrated below:

The CARARE Facebook group currently has 111 members who are actively using the facility to post links and ask questions about the project in a range of different languages. The Facebook group is illustrated below:

facebook

europeana
carare project

- Message all members
- Promote Group with an Advert
- Edit group settings
- Edit members
- Invite people to join
- Create group event
- Leave Group

Write something about CARARE - Connecting Archaeology and Architecture to Europeana.

Information

Category:
Internet & Technology - Websites

Description:
CARARE is a best practice network funded by the European Commission's ICT Policy Support Programme. It aims to bring together heritage agencies and organisations, archaeological museums and research institutions and specialist digital solutions to establish a network that

CARARE - Connecting Archaeology and Architecture to Europeana

Wall
Info
Discussions
Photos
Video
Events

Write something...

Attach: Share

Victor Iglesias Pascau

Arqueología y Patrimonio
arqueologiaypatrimonio.blogspot.com
Publicado en Patrimoni.gencat.cat Si hace unas semanas conocíamos los resultados del estudio del cuerpo del rey Pedro el Grande, ahora se presentan los primeros análisis hechos en los restos de su hijo, Jaume II, y a la esposa de éste, Blanca de Anjou. ...

📅 06 May at 23:33 · Comment · Like · Share · Flag

🔍 Options

Julia Moras Righetti Quisiera información sobre carare project. En español (spanish) si fuera posible.

04 May at 16:56 · Comment · Like · Flag

Kate Fernie I will ask our Spanish partner if they have some information in Spanish about the project

07 May at 10:04 · Delete

Write a comment...

Kate Fernie I think this competition will be of interest to some members of the group - EuroMed and RehabiMed are inviting people to submit photos of archaeological sites and ancient buildings, urban and rural landscapes and settlements, traditional houses ... in the Mediterranean region.

EUROMED
www.euromedheritage.net
A photography competition that aims at valorising photos reflecting Mediterranean cultural heritage in all its richness and diversity; a diversity that embraces archaeological sites and ancient buildings, ...

📅 04 May at 09:22 · Comment · Like · Share

👍 Stella Montanari likes this.

4. Dissemination materials

A selection of images has been made available by project partners for use in dissemination materials and on the website. A snapshot of the gallery included on the project website is shown below.

Information sheets

A template has been prepared in MS Word to facilitate the preparation of information sheets by partners for publication on the project website and for printing and circulation at professional conferences and events.

A range of information sheets are planned:

- Project briefing sheet
- Partner content fact sheets
- Technology briefing sheets

The CARARE project fact sheet is illustrated below.

CARARE

Bringing content for archaeology and historic buildings to Europeana users.

Contacts

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Subscribe to CARARE news by registering on the project website
www.carare.eu

CARARE (Connecting ARchaeology and ARchitecture in Europeana) will work with Europe's network of heritage agencies to establish an aggregation service that will bring 2 million items for Europe's unique archaeological monuments, historic buildings and heritage places into Europeana and will establish the methodology for adding 3D and Virtual Reality content to Europeana. CARARE is a Best Practice network which began in February 2010.

CARARE

- Project basics
- CARARE and Europeana
- Partners
- Further information

Project basics

CARARE is designed to involve and support Europe's network of heritage agencies and organisations, archaeological museums and research institutions and specialist digital archives in:

- making the digital content for the archaeology and architectural heritage that they hold available through Europeana,
- aggregating content and delivering services, and
- enabling access to 3D and Virtual Reality content through Europeana.

CARARE will play an important role in ensuring that digital content for Europe's unique archaeological monuments, architecturally important buildings, historic town centres and industrial monuments of World, European and National heritage importance is interoperable with Europeana and accessible alongside contents from national libraries, archives, museums and other content providers. CARARE aims to enable 2D and 3D content for heritage places to be brought together in Europeana and new services for users.

CARARE, which runs from 1 February 2010 until January 2013, is funded under the European Commission's ICT Policy Support Programme and co-ordinated by [KulturArvstyrelsen](#) (Denmark) with [MDR Partners](#) (UK). The project consortium consists of 29 partners from 20 countries across Europe.

CARARE and Europeana

The Europeana service offers access to millions of digital items provided by Europe's museums, galleries, archives, libraries and audio-visual organisations. Some of these are world famous, others are as yet hidden treasures. Europeana will deliver access to over 10 million digital objects by 2010.

CARARE is funded by the European Commission's [ICT Policy Support Programme](#)

A template has been prepared for PowerPoint presentations. This template was used to produce a presentation giving an introduction to the CARARE project covering:

- CARARE in a nutshell
- Vision
- Europeana background
- CARARE workplan
- Partners
- Website

The slides are illustrated below:

The CARARE Essential PowerPoint has been used as the starting point to prepare presentations for conferences and events.

5. References

CARARE Description of Work